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A Innovation Research of Economy Development Indicator like GDP and High-Technology Products & Following Education on Senior Scientists Sustainably

Run^{1*}, Wanhao Wu²

¹ Gyeongsang National University, School of Nano New Materials Engineering, Jinju-Si 52828,
Gyeongnam-Do, Korea (Rep)

² Yantai Institute of Science & Technology, Yantai 264005, Shandong Province, China

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Corresponding author:

Run^{1*}

¹ Gyeongsang National
University, School of Nano
New Materials Engineering,
Jinju-Si 52828, Gyeongnam-
Do, Korea (Rep)

Abstract

With regards to the high-tech skill and products the research on them will become necessary and important currently by Scientists who has pursued those high-tech searching for producing innovation product urgently. So that we may participate in the new machine even robot service expenses which may bring out many new idea and method for us to continuously push those innovation products forwards sustainably. Therefore, the new employment will be realized for those graduates from college annually and meanwhile, the high-tech product supply chains can carry out many new opportunities gradually and eventually. There will be a much more big space in the huge chains which is not neglected at all though they may process one special part there is still many those OEMs (original equipment manufacturers) for making a final product completion at the down-stream makers. As we knew the hundred parts will assemble one complete product, so the technique transfers to the up-stream OEM will be important which we are named the technology transfer for their survival to look for more working chances. On the other side, the scientist will still be publishing their achievement on a famous journal for us to identify and use which can shorten down our research time and times for the sake of being convenient to use on our research to create another product in time.

Keywords: innovation research; GDP & economy development; high-technology product; education; sustainably; senior scientist

1. Introduction

In current society the high-technique products will be dominated in others to become a strong force to push the society to develop continuously and sustainably, so the scientist and scholars will become an important factor to play in every place to proceed the relevant research and study on the hot point frequently. So that publishing achievement papers may provide a strong force to support the future life-level like climate change and public sanitation for benefiting the world human in future. We should go on searching for innovation papers include in the latest high-technique product research like clean energy and new one to push many lots of skill to make different cutting-edge-field product continually. As we knew the current climate problem will be derived from the contaminating factory and automobile, so the new energy should occupy the first significant position for our scholar & scientist and experts to sustainably search and make measure to solve it from variation views which may help us to think about more factors to replace the problems mutually. We might align the measure from one view to different one to proceed simulate to judge the first and the second even third method to solve it for the sake of once happening the problem accident there will be another method to replace it in urgency. [1~6] So we put our eyes too long not only viewing the current status but also looking at the longer years like fairy tale cinema which provide future world several hundred years later. We may interest in those splendid scenery and consider the usefulness and make some experiments to trial the feasibility, like the flight automobile which pass by the high buildings and make a dormitory in the one. There will not earth surface auto and all the auto can become flight one which is a future plan by USA fairy cinema maker. There may be not contamination gas and all of atmosphere is electric power and hydrogen fuel even small nuclear reaction pile as an engine. So we must emphasize the current energy exploitation and found so as to predict to make a plan to prepare the future infrastructure and write more paper with innovation method to arouse the future contribution. With the GDP(gross domestic product) enhancement we should not avoid to enter the ideal world with many robots in AI(artificial intelligence) software and automobiles with intelligent driving time many decades years later, so we prepare to afford the controlling skill to fix robots logical life and automobile matters with those high energy fuel. As to the former the controlling will be proceeding from now on and its equipment needs to enter our live life many years later and the latter will experience safe driving course with no accident. Those problems will must think about by us in advance or the error ones and accident may occur by then. [7~8]

2. Discussions

With regards to developing economy and high-tech status year by year our society will be sustaining an innovation stage where many of us meet the new department and subject challenge so that we must prepare to grasp skill and product feature proficiently in advance for the sake of wielding them in future occupation life. We should carefully and boldly educate the talents and scientists through professor and tutor having a certain level and experiences continually. Meanwhile the young post-doctorate researcher should be educated so as to succeed the important task some time later like continue to complete the new subject. The qualified one may be appointed to be an associate professor and senior researcher to take a burden to educate the MS (Master of Science) & PhD (Philosophy of Doctor) degree continuously. Because they had some and much opportunities to complete the relevant projects singly and collaboratively which belongs to the high-tech

product experimental and theoretical deduction. Thereby those ones includes in many innovative methods and calculations correspondingly. At the same time, the reports and papers will be submitted to the Fund commission which may be speared through the relevant scientists. [9~15]

2.1 About Suntext Reviews

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2.2 The role of fellow in the relationship between GDP and high-tech product

The role of fellow & scientists in the relationship between promoting GDP and high-tech product would see the Figure 1 where the former could play a role from high-tech behavior and judgement into the GDP promotion through playing their effectiveness there. Thereby the good circulation can be formed continuously which boosts the society to develop eventually. So the high-tech behavior and judgement will become the center position affected by the fellow & scientists, which may push the region and country economy sustainable development.

Figure 1 The role of fellows in GDP and High-tech relationship.

2.3 The Journal of Medical and Clinical Nursing Studies introduction

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We would be honored to receive your manuscript for consideration. Kindly submit your article as an attachment directly to this email. We will provide the cheaper fee for processing your one promptly and quickly for the sake of affording to publish conveniently. We look forward to your esteemed contribution, which we believe will enrich the academic discourse in medical and clinical nursing studies. [2]

2.4 USA top states' GDP analysis

The USA top five states GDP would display 1.9~0.588 trillion dollars in light of Figure 2 in 2009 whose variation arrived in 3.27 times maximum by California~Pennsylvania state accordingly. Meanwhile, the ones beyond 1 trillion dollars might indicate California and Texas two states then expressed their strong economy strength and entities.

Figure 2 The USA top states' GDP ranking in 2009. [3]

Meantime, the Guangdong~Ohio GDP value might express 0.58~0.49 trillion dollars in 2009 in terms of Figure 3 by two countries' state & provinces where the variation arrived in 1.2 times maximum. On the other side, their value beyond 0.5 trillion dollars indicated Guangdong & Jiangsu two regions explaining their good economic status.

Figure 3 The USA & Chinese top state & provinces' GDP ranking in 2009. [3]

2.5 Canadian & Chinese top provinces analysis

The Canada & China top four provinces would exhibit 640~50 billion dollars in light of Figure 3 in 1996 by Canada~Henan one respectively where the variation time might 12.8 time with large value to express the former good economic status. On the other side, there were three ones whose GDP exceeded 100 billion dollars, and they were Canada, Taiwan & Guangdong province in turns.

Figure 4 The Canadian & Chinese top provinces' GDP ranking in 1996. [3]

2.6 The GDP and education relationship

The GDP and employment level besides education relationship would be showed in Figure 4 where college education plus R&D proceeded by Master and PhD course students in college could increase employment level & capacity and GDP simultaneously. Meanwhile, the employment level and GDP & products might act on each other mutually to explain the education and R&D important role on them ultimately. So it will say that the college education plus R&D will play a significant role in advance who may form the GDP and employment improvement. Thereby, we should enhance our capabilities through educating ourselves relevant subjects so as to progress our R&D capabilities. Not only upon independence by ourselves, but also collaboration by co-operation with others may create our R&D ability actually. We might remember the sentence to proceed our project in order to boost the making innovation product ability at all.

Figure 5 The education and GDP & employment relationship. [4~7]

2.7 The Chinese PC sale amount

The Chinese PC sale amount and y-y value will display 68~42 million and 20%~5% by 2021~2025E respectively in terms of Figure 5 whose variation time might attain 1.6 times and 4.2 times with maximum expressed the declining trend. [8] Meantime, the lowest sale amount and y-y value might attain 41 million in 2024 and -20% in 2023 respectively to explain the depressive situation then. According to the economist prediction the one in 2025 & 2026 will afford 40 & 42 million and 0~5% y-y with a little increasing to compare with past year. [8]

Figure 6 The China PC sale amount & y-y. [8]

2.8 Stocks change

The difference between special constitution and individual would include as below. As for the individual customer there are 1. delaying information. Hearing information and seeing spare document; 2. defecting investigation. Only seeing the technology morphology, transaction amount and turnover ration etc. 3. blindly chasing trend. After buying it declines and after selling it increases, at last randomly cutting meat. 4. random operation. Randomly thinking about occasionally and chasing increase & killing decline, frequently operated. [9] On contrast, the special team tactic includes in following. 1. Team work. There are analytical division, tactic division and operating diversity co-operation; 2. Speciality. The constitution unions investigation, and speciality message to share; 3. Eye-light. Understanding the main behavior and management layer's market management intention; 4. Operation plates. Making picture to show the customers in order to enhance & attract capital kept up. [10]

3. Conclusions

The education work could be proceeded continually by not only college teachers and but also R&D senior experts who might teach the students and staffs the required knowledge and experiences periodically like half an year, so the new ones could grasp and understand the entire and key joints to use in later work like a new method. After a certain time the achievement done by them will be evaluated by the upper leader to give the score in order to reward and punish them. So the excellent one may be promoted into a higher layer to lead others making their work with trial. They will nominate the detailing work normally if they make a better achievement within that period. On the other side, the company with those excellent talents and experts may create the new dynamic to enhance the economy indicator like GDP growth continuously commonly. Those unemployment amount will be declined if the GDP growth continually and on the contrary those men can enhance the economy level towards higher level progression. They will be mutually acting and affecting relationship, so that the products would be formed through constantly innovating and design by the good R & D researchers who master one and several key contents to complete his programme sustainably. Finally the promoting GDP value can refer to the variation between the better and worse situation according to investigate individual region like province and city & county scale to define the fittest growth speed with stabilization continually. From there the default and advantage will be found definitely, we should constantly insist on the big eye-light to develop each GDP value for next two years.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declared that there were not conflicts of interest to disclose.

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